

Parenting Support for Parents in Difficulty: An Operational Model

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Abstract

Various studies have shown that almost all behavioural and learning problems in children are caused by adults creating the conditions for the learning of inappropriate behaviours. This occurs either because they do not know how to deal with the child's problem behaviours, or because they know what to do but are completely unable to implement it.

The need to work directly with parents to promote the development of children with atypical development, considering parents as co-therapists, has been summarised by the term "parent training". But do parents really need to be "trained", "reprimanded" or "corrected" in the performance of their institutional role? Definitely NOT.

Parents do not have a deficiency or a problem that requires specific training. Rather, they are people who need help in the daily task of parenting a child with a neurodevelopmental disorder. An alternative, broader and more inclusive term for Parent Training, which encompasses various interventions aimed at supporting parents in their difficult daily role, is "Parenting Support".

Introduction

The experiences that will have a decisive impact on a child's personality development initially take place in the family environment and later also at school. It is with their parents that children spend most of their time. This does not mean, however, that all parents fully understand the impact that their parenting methods, relationships with their children and expectations of them have on their children. Many parents, in fact, unintentionally promote inappropriate behaviour in their children [1].

Various studies [2] have shown that almost all behavioural and learning problems in children are created by adults who create the conditions for the learning of inappropriate behaviours. This occurs either because they do not know how to deal with the child's problem behaviours, or because they know what to do but are completely unable to do it.

The most common mistakes that educators can unknowingly make that cause and perpetuate problems in their children are as follows [3]:

1. *Reinforcing inappropriate behaviour.* Behaviour can be reinforced even against one's will, for example,

when parents only pay attention to their child when they display dysfunctional behaviour. This type of attention, however negative it may be (punishment), often constitutes a generalised reinforcer that consolidates the behaviour on which it depends.

2. *Ignoring appropriate behaviour.* A common parenting mistake is failing to reward or acknowledge children when they behave appropriately. Often, behind this attitude is the belief that when children behave appropriately, they are simply doing their duty and should therefore understand on their own that certain other behaviours are inappropriate.

3. *Having excessive expectations.* Many parents rely heavily on their children's abilities to meet their own unfulfilled needs, but expectations are often matched by a changed attitude towards their children, who are perceived as *brilliant* or *slow* learners. It is inevitable that children will react to excessive pressure and demands with anxiety, avoidance or escape behaviours, or phobic reactions. Parents of children with atypical development must first overcome their deep sense of mistrust in their children's learning and recovery potential, then modify overprotective or

More Information

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rejecting attitudes that can block or delay adaptive learning processes [4,5]. In the case of overprotection, for example, parents underestimate their child's potential and consider them completely incapable and in need of greater care and attention, which prevents them from developing many skills that they would otherwise be able to acquire. In the case of rejection, on the other hand, this manifests itself either through open hostility or by ignoring the child, persuading parents not to provide adequate stimuli for the acquisition of new skills and not to provide appropriate rehabilitation measures in a timely manner.

4. *Creating an inadequate educational environment.* Many parents fail to create an environment that promotes learning and do not employ strategies to encourage it. This occurs either because negative reinforcement is used too often, triggering escape or avoidance behaviours in the child, or because adaptive behaviour is not reinforced adequately. The need that arises from these considerations is that parents need to know what to do when faced with the often very serious behaviours exhibited by children. Another objective is to determine if there is a discrepancy between what parents believe their child can do and what the child can do.

5. *Communicating in a dysfunctional way.* Parents often communicate with their children using inappropriate language or because they are unclear and use “nuances” that the child does not understand, or by using expressions such as “You're always the same, you always rush things” (or worse), ridiculing or devaluing them, “Look at the nice work your brother has done, he's younger than you”.. This damages their self-esteem and does not improve their relationship with the adult.

At this point, it should be emphasised that behaviours controlled by the events they themselves produce in the environment and that follow them belong to the class of operating interactions. This class also includes educational styles that exert their function on behaviour regardless of whether they are intentional.

Educational Styles

As we have seen, there are many factors that contribute to determining a child's behaviour. Among these, in addition to genetic and environmental factors, which contribute equally to defining the traits of everyone, educational factors can modify the child's natural environment by producing stimuli capable of changing future behaviour, even in a “pathological” direction. In fact, many emotional and behavioural disorders in children are due to disturbed parenting styles. These styles can be classified as follows [6]:

1. *Overprotective style.* Parents who adopt this style tend to avoid any frustration for the child and shower them with excessive and indiscriminate displays of affection. They also underestimate their child's

potential, considering them completely incapable and in need of greater care and attention, which prevents the child from developing many skills that they would otherwise be able to acquire self-determination, adequate tolerance of frustration, anxiety control and preparation for dealing with situations other than those they are used to in their family environment.

2. *Hyper-anxious style.* “Hyper-anxious” parents are afraid of everything: “Johnny, don't climb on the chair, you could fall and break your head”, “Maria, put your coat on, it's cold and you could catch bronchopneumonia”, etc. Children of parents who adopt this parenting style are shy, fearful and insecure.

3. *Hypercritical style.* This style is characterised by excessive reprimands, ridicule, sarcastic comments and belittling of the child: criticism of the person rather than the behaviour. The parent also completely ignores the child's appropriate behaviour; behind this attitude is the belief that when the child behaves appropriately, they are simply doing their duty and should therefore understand for themselves the inappropriateness of certain other behaviours. The hypercritical parent causes the child to fear making mistakes, to avoid certain situations and to have low self-esteem.

4. *Perfectionist style.* Many parents rely heavily on their children's abilities to satisfy their own unmet needs. Those who adopt this style tend to demand very high standards of performance and communicate to the child that they are only worthy of love if they succeed in everything they do. The child adopts this attitude and learns to fear disapproval and rejection if they do not achieve optimal results. This leads them to feel anxious when faced with a test (competitions, exams, tests, etc.), as the possibility of making a mistake is considered a defeat.

5. *Inconsistent style.* Children must be able to grasp the distinguishing features of the different courses of action available to them at any given moment. In this way, they learn to distinguish between right and wrong behaviour. However, they cannot learn when identical behaviours lead to opposite reactions (the child throws a tantrum to get an ice cream, the parents give in on some occasions and punish them on others), or when opposite behaviours receive the same treatment (the child is always punished, no matter what they do). If there is educational inconsistency, therefore, the child will tend to bring order to his world independently, choosing the path of opportunism (“I do what I want!”) or deviant opposition to the questionable authority represented by parents and teachers. A classification of educational inconsistency, which can be considered one of the main factors determining emotional disorders and deviant behaviour in children, includes the following types [3,7]:

a. *Intra-parental inconsistency.* This is when inconsistency is practised by a single parent. A system

of rewards and punishments is established, but the parent allows themselves many *exceptions*. For example, the parent sets a rule and punishes the child when they break it, but in certain other circumstances, the child is no longer punished but reinforced: the child is not punished at home for using bad language, but if they use bad language in front of other people, the parent punishes them immediately; in yet another circumstance, the parent does not punish the child, and so on. Therefore, failure to comply with the code of conduct, based on unpredictable fluctuations in the parent's mood, has the effect of undermining the credibility of the parental figure.

b. Inter-parental inconsistency. In families where there is no agreement on the rules of behaviour to be taught to children, it is easy to find cases of inter-parental inconsistency; for example, the father sets the rules, while the mother allows all kinds of transgressions. In this way, the child learns to orient his behaviour according to the presence of one or the other parent. On the other hand, situations in which parental disagreement is not determined by issues of role or prestige, but only by conflict for its own sake (the father and mother argue over trivial matters), are very neurotic: these conflicts are due to a relationship problem.

c. Inconsistency between values and facts. The values indicated by educational figures do not always correspond to facts: values that have been painstakingly cultivated, such as honesty, loyalty, etc., prove to be completely inadequate for dealing with life situations.

d. Inconsistency between message and reception. Parents often formulate instructions in a way that the child cannot follow, regardless of their behaviour. For instance, it is common to tell a child, "Behave yourself when you are at your friend's house!"

If educational inconsistency is a dominant pattern, the child will not learn that certain behaviours are acceptable in some situations and not in others; moreover, they may exhibit inappropriate behaviours (anxiety, fear, phobias, aggression, etc.) that may become the only responses they are able to express or avoid interactions with educational figures as much as possible (withdrawal from ordinary family situations, selective mutism, etc.) or avoid unpleasant consequences and seek pleasant ones in ways that are contrary to the educational intentions of adults [8-11]. From this perspective, the factors that define and describe interaction in the setting take on particular importance.

Factors and Interactions of the Setting

Each individual interacts continuously and reciprocally with events and objects in the environment, in which most of a person's behaviours are a combination of effective interactions (a component of the response

has a direct effect on some aspects of the environment), linguistic (the communicative or symbolic process is learned and maintained by the operating paradigm), cognitive (an activity of knowledge of antecedent stimuli) and affective (an emotional activity associated with any antecedent stimulus) [3]. The behaviour of the individual, therefore, should not be studied in isolation, but in interaction with the context.

In fact, different characteristics can be isolated from each behaviour that attribute a particular meaning to the behaviour itself, so that it can be interpreted according to the characteristic under examination.

If, for example, we analyse aggressive behaviour based on *emotional-affective characteristics*, attention will be focused on those variables that can induce aggression, such as frustration, failure, etc. From this point of view, aggressive behaviour is interpreted in terms of emotions that certain people or situations can arouse at a given moment and in each context. Each individual characteristic highlights one or more properties of the behaviour analysed and determines an interpretation that, in any case, helps to clarify the phenomenon [12,13].

When interacting with other people, our behaviour depends not only on what others do or say, but also on the interpretation we give to their behaviour based on our actions.

Social adaptation in different situations of interaction depends on the ability to adapt one's behaviour to that of other people, to the different conditions of the surrounding environment and to the moment in which the behaviour occurs. We can therefore define *social skills* as those behaviours that are effective in achieving the set goals without causing situations of interaction characterised by conflict. In other words, social skills refer to the repertoire of verbal and non-verbal behaviours through which children influence the behaviour of other individuals (peers, parents, teachers, siblings, etc.) with whom they interact. A socially *competent* person is, therefore, someone who is able to reconcile their own goals with those of others without either party having to give up an advantage. Interpersonal behaviour, understood as a social skill, is the result of a very complex cognitive activity.

The ability to interact satisfactorily with others depends on two factors: 1) our ability to solve problems and 2) the level of control we exercise over our emotions. Socially disabled people are generally characterised by high emotional involvement in social interaction. This involvement leads to unplanned behavioural strategies, which are the result of poor cognitive processing of social situations [14].

The ability to initiate and maintain positive social contacts is considered by many to be an essential stage of development. Every interaction with others provides

children with an important opportunity to learn and use social skills, the presence or absence of which can influence their subsequent social, emotional and academic adjustment. Social behaviours are taught indirectly and learned automatically in each of the countless opportunities for interaction that arise in everyday life. In this sense, school is considered an important agent of socialisation for children. Nevertheless, the school system has not yet directly addressed the development of social skills. The presence of adequate socio-emotional repertoires, therefore, allows for a progressive expansion of these repertoires; their absence, on the contrary, often leads to “adaptive” responses attributable to the dominance of problem behaviours [15].

Many behaviours should be taught in natural environments (where they would normally occur). If our goal is to train individuals to act as independently as possible in community life, educators must set aside the idea of relying entirely on a “simulated” teaching model and instead adopt a “functional” model: for example, to pursue the goal of “improving fine motor skills”, we should not use the strategy of “manipulating plasticine” (a non-functional activity), but rather that of “opening the front door with a key” (a functional activity). The belief that certain non-functional activities are necessary for children to tackle more complex activities is still widespread among educators and is responsible for “fragmented” learning that has no everyday functionality: as a result, a 20-year-old may be able to insert pegs into a pegboard but not be able to insert a key into a lock.

Effective interaction between adults and individuals with atypical development is a valuable tool that should be “exploited” by educators to facilitate the desired behaviour. Maintaining a positive relationship is essential for achieving constructive changes in the child's behaviour and facilitating training in the following areas: 1) eliminating negative emotional reactions, 2) intensifying motivation, 3) placing greater value on social reinforcement, 4) promoting communication, and 5) improving interpersonal relationships.

Parents, therefore, can fulfil the fundamental task in this educational process as educational mediators (between individualised learning and community integration) only by activating appropriate training programmes.

Parent Training

The need to act directly on parents to promote the development of children with atypical development began in the early 1970s, especially in Anglo-Saxon countries. During those years, research in the field of learning aimed to verify the validity developed by experts for individuals with atypical development. The operational context was almost exclusively institutional

(centres, special schools, etc.). Much of the educational activity, in addition to the objectives pursued, consisted of trying to control the most relevant variables underlying the learning process.

Experience clearly showed that when educational programmes were implemented correctly, the subject usually learned the skills taught very quickly. However, there were many surprises when it came to assessment, i.e. when it was necessary to evaluate the extent to which learning was retained in other environments, such as the family and school. In most of the situations observed, the skills that had been so painstakingly acquired quickly disappeared. One of the main causes was that, in the contexts analysed, the same conditions in which the learning had taken place (type of instructions, stimulus configurations, feedback, etc.) had not been maintained. In fact, when the subject found himself in his natural environment, the consistency of the intervention was almost completely lost and, with it, the improvements achieved. This research clearly highlighted the causes of the subject's poor performance in different environments. The problem was linked to the failure to implement educational interventions aimed at promoting the “generalisation” of skills acquired in structured contexts (rehabilitation centres, schools, etc.). The objective was therefore to identify new strategies to promote generalisation mechanisms, and a project and operating method aimed at the direct involvement of parents was devised [3].

This involvement of parents, considered as co-therapists, has been summarised by the widely used term “parent training” [16]. But do parents necessarily need to be “trained”, “reprimanded” or “corrected” in the performance of their institutional role? Definitely NOT. Parents do not have a deficiency or a problem that requires specific training. Rather, they are people who need help in the daily parenting of a child with a neurodevelopmental disorder, working alongside the professionals who work with the child, but without replacing them. An alternative, broader and more inclusive term for Parent Training, which includes various interventions aimed at supporting parents in their difficult everyday role, is Parenting Support. From now on, we will use the term Parenting Support (PS) instead of Parent Training [36].

Parenting Support

Improving the quality of the parent-child relationship is essential for both typically developing children and those with ASD or other intellectual disabilities. As we have seen, the quality of the relationship has a significant impact on various aspects of childhood, including development, emotionality, cognitive abilities, behaviour, interpersonal relationships, etc. This relationship can be supported and strengthened by the combined action of traditional behavioural

intervention with parents and procedures to increase psychological flexibility and reduce the emotional burden on parents of children.

Parenting Support (PS) consists of a series of informative and educational activities aimed at providing parents with specific skills related to behavioural methodologies in education, in order to make them increasingly autonomous in the education of their children. The aim of a PS programme is to promote positive parenting and reduce behavioural risks in children. Numerous studies [17-19] have demonstrated the effectiveness of these interventions in improving children's behavioural performance, increasing parents' ability to manage their children and reducing the presence of problem behaviours. However, these studies did not examine changes in parents' psychological well-being, i.e. they did not offer an effective solution for modifying their behaviour by influencing stress levels through social support and new coping strategies.

Parental participation in most PS programmes is implemented in two different ways [20,21]:

1. Parents are involved in the programme as “agents of change”. In this view, their role is mainly to implement programmes and strategies that have been previously developed by the psychologist. In this case, therefore, parents mainly learn to use specific techniques for problems and are unlikely to be able to deal adequately with new problems.

2. A different role is to consider parents as “learning technologists”. In this view, parents study and learn the basic principles of experimental psychology and models of Applied Behaviour Analysis. As a result of this process, the family should be able to choose from time-to-time which course of action to take, which learning to encourage in their child, etc. This training method also offers the advantage of ensuring considerable independence and flexibility in the way parents act.

With the second approach, the parent becomes the author of the behaviour modification programme, thus redefining the parent-consultant relationship, in which the consultant becomes the “supervisor” of the “child-natural environment” interaction.

The two models have similar content, although each is characterised by the way in which the counselling is implemented:

- *for groups of parents*, whose objectives are to provide knowledge about the factors that regulate learning processes, to control variables, to present assessment tools and techniques, to present intervention strategies, and to learn how to manage conflict and stress.

- *for individual families*, whose objectives are: to analyse the emotional content and types of responses prevalent in the educational relationship, to verbalise the anxieties and issues that prevent communication

between spouses, to highlight the causes that prevent effective interaction with the child, to choose and use alternative types of communication, to evaluate and plan the implementation of appropriate behaviours, to learn self-control strategies and to improve the emotional relationship;

In the latter case (individual), the psychologist is engaged in “therapeutic” counselling, while in the former case (groups), the action is aimed at forming a group of parents who share the same problem and in which mutual help strategies can also be activated.

Furthermore, the various elements that characterise *Parenting Support* are designed and adapted to the needs of each individual case, but the basic structure is always the same and is divided into the following phases [3]:

1. *Motivation*: creating the conditions for training, stimulating and reinforcing collaboration to avoid feelings of guilt for one's own inability and further confirmation of the impossibility of interacting adequately with one's child.

2. *Definition of the problem*: providing correct and adequate information on the extent of the problem and correctly assessing behavioural repertoires.

3. *Analysis of alternatives to solve the problem*: avoid paths already taken and found to be unproductive and identify the direction of attempts.

4. *Planning*: plan the timing of the intervention, the methods and tools to be used, etc.

5. *Gathering information*: observe and record the frequency, duration and intensity of certain behaviours, to pay more attention to the child and, at the same time, analyse your own behaviour to promote self-control.

6. *Assessing the problem*: define the problem in terms of antecedents, behaviours and consequences to highlight the stimuli and environmental situations that precede or follow the behaviour.

7. *Identification of parenting errors*: conduct a detailed analysis of the parenting errors identified in the previous stages so that they can be modified.

8. *Transfer of skills*: use the behavioural models learned at the cognitive level.

9. *Implementation of the intervention*: implement the strategies through which the behaviour can be changed.

10. *Verification*: monitor the progress of the treatment and make appropriate modifications to the programme.

However, the validity and effectiveness of *Parenting Support* can be compromised by the following variables [22]:

1. *Subject-related variables*. The presence of a child with problems can exacerbate certain marital disharmonies.

2. *Variables related to the parents.* Problems between parents and children are often related to other issues: marital conflicts, depression, socio-cultural isolation, etc.

3. *Socio-economic variables.* A low social and economic status can create difficulties in family interaction.

Despite the presence of these variables, Parenting Support enables parents to manage problematic situations independently, without resorting to external intervention, except in cases where highly specialised expertise is truly necessary. But how is a Parenting Support programme structured?

A PS programme, whether individual (single parent or couple) or group, is divided into several phases, each of which aims to provide parents with tools and strategies to improve the behavioural management of their children. The group approach is preferable, as it promotes understanding and sharing of different parenting experiences and strategies, opening parents up to discussion and exposure to a wide variety of parenting styles. The group, which consists of 5-6 couples (any dropouts are not replaced), is grouped according to the age and diagnosis of their children, helping to overcome social isolation and reduce levels of anxiety and anger. The programme lasts for 10-15 sessions of 90-120 minutes, held weekly or, preferably, fortnightly.

Operational Model

Parenting Support interventions generally have two different levels: 1) *Knowledge* (what the disorder is, its causes, how it is diagnosed, symptoms, available treatments and therapies, etc.) and 2) *Know-how* (definition of behaviour; observation techniques; skill teaching models; management of dysfunctional behaviours, etc.). Our operational model, inspired in part by ACT, includes another level: 3) *Knowing how to be* (learning psychological skills to relate to one's own painful thoughts and emotions, inspiring, guiding and motivating oneself to change one's life for the better and to have greater awareness, etc.) (Fig. 1). This model, which is also based on behaviour analysis, facilitates implementation in clinical practice while avoiding the main criticisms levelled at interventions based exclusively on levels 1 and 2 [23]: 1) their overly structured nature, 2) their lack of naturalness, and 3) their insensitivity to the child's developmental changes. In addition, these interventions may accidentally reinforce parental behavioural rigidity as a "side effect" of successful interventions with children. And, according to the contextual-functional approach, there are no absolute right or wrong techniques, selected solely on the basis of the behavioural history of the person with atypical development, but there are strategies that are more or less effective within a given context and at a given time, also depending on

the *emotional availability* of the significant actors operating and acting in that context [24].

Starting from these assumptions, the authors of this work have structured a *Parenting Support* intervention, either individual or group-based, that is more sensitive to the psychological health of the main agents of change and support in the child's life. In other words, they support a model of parenting that is psychologically flexible and sensitive to change [25,26] (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2).

The intervention includes a preliminary phase in which a thorough analysis of parenting support needs is carried out: on medical information and access to care (e.g., diagnostic pathway and other organic problems; *in-depth skills*), on the level of parental awareness of the child's behavioural functioning profile and expressed educational needs (*parental skills*), on information about the service and the services working together (*guidance skills*), on internal barriers (*emotional skills*) and external barriers (*environmental skills*). This is followed by an operational phase in which the actual intervention is structured, differentiating between individual and group intervention:

Purpose	The programme has specific objectives	Levels
General Target	Training Units (TU) divided into three levels	Ensure that parents achieve adequate levels of independence and flexibility in their actions.
Specific Target	The objectives are explained within a three-level cost taxonomy.	Knowledge (L1): what the disorder is, its causes, diagnosis, symptoms, treatments and therapies available, etc.
		Know-how (L2): observation techniques; skill teaching models; management of dysfunctional behaviour, etc. Knowing how to be (L3): learning psychological skills to relate to one's own thoughts and painful emotions, inspiring, guiding and motivating oneself to change one's life for the better and have greater awareness, etc.

Figure 1: Structure of a Parenting Support Course

TU	N	Contents
KNOWLEDGE	1	What is autism: causes and diagnosis.
	2	Cognitive, emotional and behavioural aspects.
	3	Learning in people with autism.
	4	What treatment to implement.
KNOW-HOW	5	How to measure behaviour.
	6	Teaching priority skills.
	7	Improving communication.
	8	Managing dysfunctional behaviour.
KNOWING HOW TO BE	9	Accepting the problem.
	10	Controlling suffering.
	11	Psychological flexibility.
	12	Psychological well-being.

Figure 2: Contents of a Parenting Support Course on Autism. The Training Unit (TU)'s Understanding Varies Depending on the Disorder Presented by the Individual (ASD, ADHD, Down syndrome, etc.)

Individual intervention. During the first meetings with the parents, or with only one of them, in addition to

“opening manoeuvres” (actions and strategies used to create a welcoming and safe environment, encouraging trust and cooperation from the parents during the initial stages of getting to know each other: these manoeuvres aim to reduce anxiety, encourage the expression of emotions regarding the problem, and lay the foundations for a positive relationship), the subject's history (discovery of problems, diagnosis, relationships with institutions, extracurricular activities and more) and the educational treatment to be implemented (clear information on how the intervention will take place, the objectives and expectations, helping parents feel more confident and prepared), it is necessary to identify the parental profile in order to calibrate the objectives and, once the profile has been drawn up for both parents, 2-3 strengths (skills that the parent already possesses and that work in their relationship with the child) and 2-3 weaknesses (skills that the parent does not yet possess, or possesses only partially, and which it is hoped can be acquired or enhanced) should be selected (Fig. 3). The profile should be drawn up at the end of the first meeting, at the end of half of the meetings and at the end of the PS programme.

The individual PS intervention involves 10-15 biweekly meetings lasting approximately 90 minutes each. Depending on the number of meetings scheduled, the trainer will adapt the content shown in Fig. 2 to the parental profile, choosing the following operational strategies, tailored to the various situations:

- 1) *Contextual videos*. Parents must make videos in the home environment on specific topics, focusing on the interaction between parent and child. The videos will then be viewed together with the trainer, who will initially focus only on the child and their behaviour, highlighting their skills and commenting on positive emotions.
- 2) *Speaking for the child*: Parents speak on behalf of the child to explain behaviours and emotions from the child's point of view (in the first or third person).
- 3) *Ask questions*. Parents ask themselves questions about why certain behaviours occur and try to come up with answers (Fig. 4).
- 4) *Add subtitles*: Parents comment on the child's behaviour (e.g., “He seems really happy here”).
- 5) *Reinforce*. The trainer positively reinforces parental behaviours that are appropriate and effective to increase the likelihood that these positive behaviours will be repeated and maintained over time.
- 6) *Recognition*. The trainer recognises the parent as the “expert” on the child.

From the third meeting onwards, the parents' weaknesses are addressed.

IDENTIFYING THE PROFILE	YES	NO	S
01. Knowing how to observe the child and describe them in operational language			
02. Identifying the child's motivations (assessment of preferences)			
03. Using positive and negative reinforcement			
04. Understanding the function of behaviours			
05. Using non-punitive strategies to manage inappropriate behaviours			
06. Knowing how to regulate one's emotions			
07. Knowing how to create learning situations			
08. Knowing how to alternate relational situations with learning situations			
09. Encouraging eye contact with the interlocutor			
10. Enhancing skills (e.g., play, imitation, pointing, etc.)			
11. Maintain your parental role			
12. Generalize the programs learned in structured contexts			
13. Encourage joint attention			
14. Know how to manage inappropriate behaviours			
15. Communicate effectively			

Figure 3: Questionnaire for Identifying the Parental Profile. ‘S’ = Sometimes

CHILD'S BEHAVIOUR	PARENTS' DOUBTS	THE SON'S QUESTIONS
Always answers NO.	Why is he behaving like this?	Why do they always tell me what to do?
Cries and jumps around in despair.	What can I do to help my child?	I feel bad. Why don't you help me?
Does not sit at the table to work.	Should I suggest school activities?	Why do I always have to do the same things?
Does not respect time limits.	What strategy should I use?	When will this task be finished?
Self-harms or hits others.	What should I do when he behaves like this?	Why don't they understand my messages?
Does not comply with requests.	Why doesn't he do what he's asked?	Why can't I do what I want?

Figure 4: Parents Express Doubts about Their Child's Behaviour, while at the Same Time Trying to Understand what Questions the Child May be Asking behind Their Behaviour

Group intervention. Parenting Support is carried out with a group of 5-6 pairs of parents, following the criterion of homogeneity in terms of the age and diagnosis of the children (for example, groups of parents with preschool children aged 3-6 years; groups of parents of primary school children aged 6-10 years; groups of parents of adolescents, grouped according to their functioning profile). The format is closed, meaning that it is not possible to replace dropouts or add new couples once the programme has started. The duration of the treatment is clearly defined in advance, ranging from 10 to 20 sessions, typically lasting 90-120 minutes, on a weekly or fortnightly basis, with a follow-up after one month.

The topics covered in the various stages of the PS programme are specific to the disorder presented by the child, and the strategies proposed are those recognised as effective for a given disorder (Fig. 1 and Fig. 2). When choosing the topics to be covered and the time to be devoted to each of them, the trainer requires parents to make a constant commitment at home, motivating them to do the homework assigned. Before the intervention, an assessment phase is necessary to evaluate the suitability of the couple for the group programme or the need to start a preliminary programme to reduce the levels of conflict between the parents. To this end, the Parenting Assessment

Questionnaire (QVG) is administered before and after the PS programme to assess the “Sense of Effectiveness”, “Parental Distress” and “Family Cohesion” (Fig. 5 and Fig. 6).

QUESTIONS	0	1	2	3
01. Responsibilities are shared with my partner				
02. I can communicate effectively with my child				
03. I am not anxious when I think about my child's future				
04. I feel that my relationship with my wife/husband has strengthened				
05. I have positive feelings towards my child				
06. I feel in control of the situation in my relationship with my child				
07. I would like to participate more in family life				
08. I can make decisions about what to do				
09. I am optimistic and confident that I can overcome difficult situations				
10. I can manage dysfunctional behaviour				
11. The family's social life is good				
12. I can change my child's behaviour				

Figure 5: Parenting Assessment Questionnaire (PAQ), where 0 corresponds to NO, Never; 1: Sometimes; 2: Often; and 3: Always. The Sum of the Scores for Each Item will be Entered in the White Box at the Bottom Right of the Questionnaire

The score is calculated by adding the scores for each individual item, dividing it by the final TS (36) and multiplying it by 100 (the same can be done with each individual component, but dividing the sum of the scores by 12 and multiplying it by 100). At the end, you will have a parenting quotient which, if perfect, will be equal to 100, with an assessment of the individual components that will allow the parent to understand what they need to improve in their PS journey.

	QUESTIONS	SA	TS	%
SENSE OF EFFICACY	02. I can communicate effectively with my child			
	06. I am in control of the situation in my relationship with my child			
	10. I can manage dysfunctional behaviour			
	12. I can change my child's behaviour		12	
PARENTAL DISTRESS	01. Responsibilities are shared with my partner			
	03. I am not anxious when I think about my child's future			
	05. I have positive feelings towards my child			
	09. I am optimistic and confident that I can overcome difficult situations		12	
FAMILY COHESION	04. I feel that my relationship with my wife/husband has strengthened			
	07. I would like to participate more in family life			
	08. I can make decisions about what to do			
	11. The family's social life is good		12	
	$\Sigma p0$		36	

Figure 6: PAQ Scoring, where SA = Score Achieved, TS = Total Score for Each of the Following Components: “Sense of Efficacy”, “Parental Distress” and “Family Cohesion”, as Well as the Total Score

After the assessment phase, the first four meetings are dedicated to “Understanding”, which refers to the disorder (ASD, SLD, ADHD, etc.) that the subject presents; The second four meetings are dedicated to “Knowing how to do”, based on the skills that parents should have in order to influence the main symptoms (e.g. social communication, imitation, play, etc.) and maladaptive behaviours, or behavioural management

of the subject (e.g. destructive behaviours, eating, sleeping, toilet training, etc.), considering that the child is the direct beneficiary of the intervention.

The last four meetings focus on “Knowing how to be” to promote psychological flexibility in parents and children, rather than relying on previous models of rigid and decontextualised rule-following. In fact, when faced with disabling and permanent problems such as autism and other neurodevelopmental disorders, PS cannot limit itself to the acquisition of adequate psychoeducational skills but must consider the emotional state of all family members.

Analysis of PS experiences has shown that the emotional state and attitude of parents towards their children's behaviour also depend on their mental state and marital relationship (understood as a factor supporting family well-being), making it necessary to introduce work on parents' “mentalisation” skills. A parent can “mentalise” if they are able to understand their child's mind and form ideas about their internal states: What do they believe? What do they think? What do they feel? How do they feel when I do/say this? (Fig. 4).

Already about 20 years ago, [27] told us about the importance for parents to be “mindful parents”, i.e. to be able to pay non-judgmental and non-reactive attention to their child's behaviour to tune in to their needs. Based on this and other assumptions, it is important to consider Mindfulness-based Parenting Support interventions [28-31] or Acceptance and Commitment Therapy (ACT) in the “Knowing how to be” Training Unit. [30] or Acceptance and Commitment Therapy [32-34], which seek to promote parents' awareness of their own “automatic pilots” and their emotional self-regulation skills. The aim of these “mindfulness” PSs is to help people build rich and meaningful lives while effectively managing the suffering, pain and stress that life inevitably brings. This can be achieved by: 1) teaching psychological skills for dealing with painful thoughts and emotions (called mindfulness skills), 2) helping people clarify what is really important and meaningful to them (e.g., their values), and 3) using this understanding to guide, inspire, and motivate them to change their lives for the better.

Conclusions

Experimental studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of PS interventions in improving children's behavioural performance, increasing parents' ability to manage their children, and reducing the presence of problem behaviours. Additionally, these studies highlight improvements in parental competence in managing children from a behavioural perspective, but without examining changes in parents' psychological well-being.

The proposed operational model, on the other hand, requires the integration of traditional behavioural intervention (Training Units 1 and 2) with Mindfulness and ACT (Training Unit 3), promoting parental well-being, child behaviour management and the parent-child relationship [29,35]. A preliminary study conducted by the authors shows that this programme is effective in reducing stress and increasing parental well-being in clinical populations (especially with people of different ages with ASD) and that these benefits are maintained after the intervention.

Psychological distress, therefore, is no longer considered to be the child's or the parents', but is defined, observed and analysed based on interactions between the individual and the environment. This implies the rejection of the medical model in favour of a psychological view of problems anchored in the methodological principles of learning theories.

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